

Modelling Specimen Size Effect in Laminated Composites

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ABSTRACT: In this study, the ability to model the experimentally observed size effect in composite materials is examined with a damage mechanics based constitutive model (CODAM). Data from the literature for an edge-notched tension specimen is used. These tensile specimens have been scaled only in the planar dimensions, keeping the thickness the same. It is shown that the CODAM model predicts a size effect for the tension specimen geometries that matches the experimentally observed size effect and the Bažant Approximate Size Effect Law. This study demonstrates that a damage mechanics model is capable of capturing the significant structural size effects that are observed experimentally, and it is suggested that such an approach provides an advantage over other methods of analysis.

KEYWORDS: Size effect; strain softening; continuum damage mechanics, finite element modelling.

INTRODUCTION

One of the challenges in composites engineering research and development is the scaling of structural response. For reasons of convenience and expense, material and structural testing is preferably performed at a small scale. Actual structures tend to be much larger than those tested in the laboratory (Figure 1). In progressing from testing on a small scale to design and use at a much larger scale, it has been observed that materials and structures do not exhibit the same level of performance at the larger scales [1]. Indeed, even scaling laboratory specimens by a factor of two or four may result in a significant change in the nominal strength or strain-to-failure of the materials [2-4]. In general, larger structures exhibit lower strengths and strains-to-failure than smaller structures. This apparent change in behaviour is called the “size effect”.

Figure 1. Notched tension specimen (left) at the centimetre scale and a wingtip spar (right) at the metre scale.

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CODAM CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

A continuum damage mechanics (CDM) model for composite laminates – CODAM – has been developed [5]. The model is an experimentally based, phenomenological approach to modelling damage growth in composite laminates. CODAM employs a set of curves, one relating the damage variables to an effective strain, and the other relating modulus reduction to the damage variables. Damage and its effects are abstracted to the sub-laminate level, allowing for some consideration of the effects of the stacking sequence and interface effects. Damage variables are defined for each of the two normal orthotropic loading directions as well as shear loading, and the damage growth and modulus reduction curves are unique in each case and sensitive to differences in compression and tension. The CODAM approach is conceptually simple and relatively easy to characterize. References [5, 6] provide greater detail.

CRACK BAND MODEL

All CDM based models share the deficiency, unless specific remedies are employed, that they exhibit mesh size sensitivity within the context of finite element analysis. CDM models typically involve strain-softening, in which the softening behaviour creates a peak stress and significant post-peak behaviour. In stress states where all elements are in the pre-peak stress regime, the size of the elements used to model the structure does not affect the analysis. However, as soon as elements pass into the post-peak stress regime, localization occurs.

As an illustration of the localization problem, consider four elements connected in series and subjected to a tensile load. Suppose that the constitutive behaviour of each element is represented by a bilinear strain-softening material (elastic-ideally fracturing) behaviour. Figure 2a illustrates these elements with a stress that remains in the elastic regime. As the load is increased, the load in each element is increased, and as long as the material remains elastic, each element has the same strain (Figure 2b). At some point however, one element becomes damaged just before the others (it transitions into the strain-softening portion of the curve), and thus for the same stress, shows a larger strain (Figure 2c). The other elements relax (unloading elastically), exhibiting less strain than they had previously experienced. Figure 2d shows the stress-strain history for element 2 (top), the early damaging element 3 (middle), and the average stress-strain history for the complete structure (bottom).

In this case, with four elements, the structure shows a certain ultimate strength and post-failure behaviour. If a different number of elements are used to model the same geometry, the post-failure behaviour will change, demonstrating the mesh effect: the more elements are used, the more abrupt the overall response, as a smaller element provides the softening contribution. This “localization” can cause severe problems, affecting global parameters such as the peak load and the strain distribution.

Early attempts to deal with localization, especially near crack tips, include the point stress and average stress theories of Whitney and Nuismer [7]. More recent approaches for removing the mesh size dependency include the cohesive crack method [8, 9], smooth particle hydrodynamics [10, 11] (similar to the element-free Galerkin method), and various nonlocal averaging schemes [12-14].

CODAM addresses the localization problem by incorporating the crack band model for mode I crack opening behaviour. The crack band model was pioneered by Rashid [15] and later detailed extensively by Bažant and Oh [16]. The essence of the approach is that every material has a characteristic height of damage, h_c , and a characteristic fracture energy, G_F , in mode I crack opening behaviour. G_F is related to the area under the stress-strain curve (γ_F^e) for the material according to Equation 1.

$$G_F = h_c \gamma_F^c \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. Illustration of one-dimensional localization.

Within the framework of finite element analysis, the crack band model dictates that the fracture energy (G_F) must be the same regardless of the size of elements used in the analysis. The softening behaviour forces localization into a single element, of height h_e , thus forcing the effective damage height to be the same as the element height. Therefore, to maintain G_F constant, one must scale γ_F^e such that Equation 2 remains valid.

$$G_F = h_c \gamma_F^c = h_e \gamma_F^e \quad (2)$$

Figure 3 illustrates the stress-strain curves produced by CODAM for an arbitrary material, showing both the curve for the characteristic height, h_c , which is not scaled, and for an element height, h_e , that is smaller than the characteristic height. As shown, the stresses and strains prior to the peak stress, with corresponding dissipated energy density γ_U , are not scaled since localization does not occur in the pre-peak stress regime.

Figure 3. Expected stress—strain curve for CODAM with an implementation of the crack band approach.

SIZE EFFECT IN COMPOSITES

Size effects are typically observed in materials that are brittle in nature. These materials tend to be sensitive to flaws within the material, and increasing the volume of material under load increases the chance of a critical flaw being present. This theory was refined by Weibull and found to be applicable to situations as diverse as the fibre strength of cotton and the breadth of beans of *Phaseolus Vulgaris* [17].

Weibull did not explicitly present his theory in terms of predicting strength of materials based on the stressed volume and the probability of that volume including a fatal flaw, but this extension is relatively trivial (for example, see Wisnom [18]). The probability of survival, $P(s)$, for a volume, V , subjected to a stress σ , is:

$$P(s) = e^{-V \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m} \quad (3)$$

where σ_0 is the reference strength and m is the Weibull modulus, a parameter that governs the shape of the distribution function. The change in failure strength can then be expressed by:

$$\sigma_2 = \sigma_1 \cdot \left(\frac{V_1}{V_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (4)$$

From Equation 4 it can be seen that according to the Weibull theory, the relative strength of materials of different sizes, yet geometrically scaled, is affected by the relative volumes and the distribution shape

factor, m . Similar equations can be developed based on the assumptions that only the length or the cross-sectional area results in a size effect.

One of the earliest investigations into size effects in composites was performed by Bullock at the General Dynamics Corporation [19]. Bullock examined two composite systems, T300/5208 carbon epoxy and Modmor II/5208 carbon epoxy, and compared the strength of tensile coupons to the strengths determined from flexural tests. Bullock also examined the strength of epoxy-impregnated strands. Comparing the results to those predicted by applying Weibull's theory, Bullock concluded that a size effect as described by Weibull does exist. Wisnom [18] notes in his review of experimental tests on composite materials for size effect that the test methods described by Bullock may have lent themselves to a systemic size effect. The problem is identified as the stress concentrations created by the grips in tension tests. The stress concentrations have a greater effect on thicker laminates rather than individual strands, and arguments have been made that this contributed to the results that Bullock observed.

From these humble beginnings, research into size effects in composites has increased and is pursued by a number of researchers worldwide. The University of Bristol has a research group headed by Wisnom that has been very actively investigating size effect in the past 15 years. In 1991, Wisnom [2] released a study that examined length-scaling effects in carbon epoxy (XAS/913) laminates. The laminates were unidirectional, and the cross-sectional area was kept constant through the tests. Based on the results of the tests, Wisnom concluded that there is a size effect, but it is more pronounced than that predicted by the Weibull theory. Further, it was shown that the variability of the results for tests at the same length was much smaller than that predicted by the Weibull theory for the given size effect.

The group continued their research, examining size effects in tension and bending specimens, and in 1999, Wisnom presented a comprehensive review of size effects in the testing of composite materials [18]. The review is limited to unnotched strength of continuous fibre reinforced composites, and concentrates on carbon epoxy and glass-fibre epoxy materials. The review discusses possible factors that would lead to size related effects in composite materials, and then reviews data presented in the literature for tensile failures (tension and flexural tests), compressive failures (end-loaded compression, flexural, and cylindrical tests), and matrix-dominated failures. There is some discussion on the applicability of Weibull's theory to describing the size effect, but the literature is inconclusive on the generality of applying this theory to all size effects in composites. Wisnom concludes that size effects are real in composite materials, and not simply an artefact of testing procedures.

In the United States, Jackson, Morton, and Kellas have collaborated for many years, investigating size effects in tension and bending tests. A number of studies were conducted through the nineties [3, 20] and continuing recently [21] where size effects and the differences in these effects due to ply sequence and method of scaling (ply-level versus sublaminar-level) have been documented. Again, significant size related effects were observed.

In 1996, Bažant et al. [4] considered single and double notched tensile tests involving 2D scaled CFRP specimens. Two layups were examined, a cross-ply layup for the double-notched tension tests, and a quasi-isotropic layup for the single notch specimens. Significant nominal strength size effect was found in both series of tests, and the results were not successfully described by either the LFM approach or the Weibull approach. Instead, Bažant et al. showed that the Bažant Approximate Size Effect Law satisfactorily predicts the effect of size. This approximate size effect law was originally developed for concrete, but has been shown to be applicable to other quasi-brittle materials. The approximate size effect law is given in Equation 5.

$$\sigma_N = Bf_u'(1 + \beta)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

where $\beta = D/D_o$ is the relative structure size, $\sigma_N = c_N P/bD$ = nominal strength of the structure, P = maximum load, D = characteristic dimension, b = width of structure, c_N = calibration coefficient, D_o = constant depending on fracture process zone and specimen size, B = constant based on plastic limit analysis, f'_u = reference strength of the material. Note that the form of Equation 5 is such that the strength is bounded by two limits: the first is the strength-based failure prediction f'_u , and the second is the fracture mechanics based square root strength reduction with increasing size. Bažant and co-workers [4, 22] have used the size effect law when dealing with concrete, rock, and toughened ceramics to reasonable success.

MODELLING SIZE EFFECT WITH CODAM

Past usage of the CODAM constitutive model has been very focussed on specific applications [6, 23-27]. These applications tended to involve numerous tests on specimens of identical size using a given material system. With a few exceptions, the same material system was not used in applications with significant size differences. Given this prior experience, the behaviour of CODAM in different size ranges was not understood, and its ability to capture size effects in composite laminates was not examined.

In order to characterize the capability of CODAM in size-scaled applications, the experimental tests and data documented by Bažant et al.[4] have been chosen as the initial application for investigation. The tests consisted of single-notched tensile (SNT) specimens involving a quasi-isotropic $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ laminate of IM7/8551-7A CFRP, as well as double-notched tensile specimens with cross-ply $[0/90_2]_s$ IM7/8551-7A CFRP. The numerical study presented here concentrates solely on the simulation of the SNT specimens.

The specimen geometries are given in Figure 4 and Table 1. The scaling involved in these experiments was two-dimensional scaling, with geometric similitude in the plane of the specimen. The thickness of the specimens remained constant at 8 plies, or 1.02 mm.

The CODAM parameters were selected according to a physically based method that considered the materials and stacking sequence [5]. The resulting CODAM parameters are listed in Table 2 while the normalized modulus ($\bar{E} = E/E^o$) versus effective strain ($F(\epsilon)$) curve and the stress-strain curve for the characteristic size are shown in Figure 5(a) and Figure 5(b), respectively.

Table 1. SNT specimen dimensions

Specimen size	w (mm)	$h=4w$ (mm)	$a=w/5$ (mm)
1	6.35	25.4	1.27
2	12.7	50.8	2.54
3	25.4	101.6	5.08
4	50.8	203.2	10.2

Figure 4. Schematic of SNT specimen.

Table 2. CODAM parameters [5] required for matching the simulated and experimentally observed nominal failure strength for SNT specimen size 3 (See Table 1)

CODAM Inputs	
Phase I (Matrix) Damage Initiation Effective Strain	0.010
Phase I (Matrix) Damage Saturation Effective Strain	0.040
Phase II (Fibre) Damage Initiation Effective Strain	0.016
Phase II (Fibre) Damage Saturation Effective Strain	0.040
Damage due to Phase I Damage Saturation	0.800
Damage due to Phase II Damage Saturation	0.200
Modulus Reduction due to Phase I Damage Saturation	0.350
Modulus Reduction due to Phase II Damage Saturation	0.650

The specimens were modelled with square elements uniformly distributed throughout the entire specimen. The smaller specimens (sizes 1 and 2) were modelled with 0.254 mm elements while the remaining specimens were modelled with 0.508 mm elements. Since the element sizes used in the simulations were considerably smaller than the characteristic height (which depended on the fracture energy, see the following section), scaling was used in the manner required by the crack band model to ensure mesh insensitivity. The use of the small elements ensured that the stress field surrounding the notch was modelled satisfactorily.

The height of damage in the specimens has been estimated to be 10 mm, corresponding to an element height of 5 mm due to the symmetry conditions used in the analyses. Incorporating this height of damage and the selected CODAM parameters results in a fracture energy of 110 mJ/mm².

Figure 6 shows that the simulations are able to predict the experiments quite well. The size effect trend is captured and the nominal strengths are predicted to reasonable accuracy. Figure 6 also shows a linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) analysis, calibrated to match the experimental average of the 25 mm wide specimen (specimen size 3), and the results of an analysis using Bažant's Approximate Size Effect Law [4]. The LEFM prediction does not adequately predict the size effect. Bažant's analysis captures the size effect quite well, but in doing so requires a fracture energy of 521 mJ/mm².

Figure 5. Normalized modulus reduction as a function of effective strain for the CODAM parameters described in Table 2 (a) and the resulting stress-strain curve (b) for the IM7/8551-7A CFRP.

Figure 6. SNT nominal strength results compared to an LEFM analysis, Bažant's Approximate Size Effect Law, and CODAM simulations.

The SNT simulations were re-examined using a height of damage that corresponded to a fracture energy of 521 mJ/mm², see Table 3. The CODAM simulations at this energy level demonstrate a degree of size effect similar to the Bažant analysis, but the nominal strength predictions are higher than the experiments (shown as a lower value in the figure). The height of damage required to achieve this fracture energy exceeds that which could reasonably be expected in experiments. Alternatively the fracture energy can be increased by changing the CODAM input parameters, but the changes required to achieve this fracture energy are so extreme that the inputs lose their physical basis.

Smaller damage heights were also examined, as shown in Table 3. The smallest damage height, 0.508 mm, corresponds to the element height in the two largest specimens and represents the results that would be expected if the mesh effect was ignored. Generally, as larger fracture energies are considered, the degree of size effect is reduced. The smaller fracture energies, equivalent to smaller damage heights, correspond to brittle responses while the larger fracture energies correspond to more ductile responses.

Table 3. Characteristic heights corresponding to specific fracture energies for the CODAM inputs. The actual damage height is twice that shown in the table due to the symmetry conditions used in the analysis.

G_F (mJ/mm ²)	h_c (mm)
11	0.508
55	2.535
110	5.069
521	23.98

SUMMARY

Structural size effects are evident in composite materials. A continuum damage mechanics model, CODAM, developed to model gross damage development in laminated composites has been shown elsewhere to adequately model a variety of applications, but previously had not been used to predict structural size effects.

This study demonstrates that CODAM is capable of simulating specimen size effects in single notch tension tests. Reasonable, physically-based estimates of the CODAM parameters incorporated with a reasonable estimate of the height of damage in the laminate combine to produce results that satisfactorily predict the nominal failure stresses and the size effect in the nominal failure stress for a range of specimen sizes. The Bazant Approximate Size Effect Law requires the use of a very high fracture energy value to fit the experimental data, while the CODAM model is able to match the experimental data with a fracture energy more in line with expectations: this discrepancy requires further study. A linear elastic fracture mechanics analysis of the same data is unable to predict the observed size effect.

This study has focussed on single notch tension tests on a single material type, scaled in two dimensions. Further study in other applications, materials, and three-dimensional scaling is required to investigate the robustness of CODAM's ability to capture size effects in composite materials.

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